

STUDIES IN THE MICHAEL CONDENSATION. PART II. SYNTHESSES OF 5-METHYL- AND 1:5-DIMETHYL-BICYCLO-0:3:4-NONANE-2:4-DIONES

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Methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-cyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetate on hydrolysis yields 2-keto-3-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetic acid. The methyl ester of the acid on condensation with either diethyl malonate or ethyl cyanoacetate, followed by hydrolysis, esterification, the Dieckmann cyclisation and decarboxylation, affords 5-methylbicyclo-0:3:4-nonane-2:4-dione. Methylation of either methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(diethyl malonate)-cyclohexylacetate or methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(ethyl cyanoacetate)-cyclohexylacetate, followed by hydrolysis, esterification, the Dieckmann reaction and decarboxylation, furnishes 1:5-dimethylbicyclo-0:3:4-nonane-2:4-dione.

The Michael condensation between diethyl malonate and an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated alicyclic ketone has been studied by Bartlett and Forrest Woods (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2933) and Mukherjee (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 155). In the following is described the synthesis of the bicyclo-0:3:4-nonane derivatives* by the application of the Michael reaction.

The hydrolysis and decarboxylation of methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxy-cyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetate (Sen Gupta and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 337) with hydrochloric acid afforded a crystalline acid ($\lambda_{\max}$ 236 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 3.84), which on esterification furnished the methyl ester ($\lambda_{\max}$ 230 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 3.85). The absorption maxima clearly indicate that the structures of the acid and its ester are represented by (I: R=H and R=Me). But the treatment of the afore-mentioned substituted β -keto ester with alkali gave an acidic material which could not be crystallised. This acidic material, on esterification, furnished a methyl ester. The ultraviolet absorption of this ester ($\lambda_{\max}$ 220 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 3.61) indicates that the major component may be represented either by the structure (II) (Shen and Whiting, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1772) or (IIA) (Shaw, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2510). The inflection at 229-232 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.55) shows also the presence of the isomeric unsaturated keto-ester (I: R=Me) in the mixture.

The condensation of diethyl malonate with the unsaturated keto-ester (I: R=Me) was performed according to Mukherjee (*loc.cit.*) to yield methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(diethyl malonate)-cyclohexylacetate (III: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂Et; R₃=Et), which, on methylation with methyl iodide and sodium either in alcohol or in benzene, afforded the methylated compound (III: R=R₁=Me; R₂=CO₂Et; R₃=Et). In order to separate easily the unmethylated ester from the methylated product, the Michael condensation was performed with ethyl cyanoacetate to afford methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(ethyl cyanoacetate)-cyclohexylacetate which, on treatment with methyl iodide and alcoholic sodium ethoxide, furnished (III: R=R₁=Me; R₂=CN; R₃=Et).

* A preliminary report appeared in the *Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 549.

The compounds (III: $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $R_3=Et$ and $R=Me$; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CN$; $R_3=Et$), on treatment with acid, followed by esterification, afforded dimethyl 2-keto-3-methylcyclohexane-1:6-diacetate. The latter, on cyclisation with sodium methoxide in benzene, followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the resulting β -keto ester with acid, afforded 5-methylbicyclo-o:3:4-nonane-2:4-dione (IV: $R=H$). It may be mentioned that the dicarboxylic acid (III: $R=R_1=R_2=R_3=H$), on pyrolysis with lead carbonate, did not furnish any desired dione.

The methylated esters (III: $R=R_1=Me$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $R_3=Et$ and $R=R_1=Me$; $R_2=CN$; $R_3=Et$), when subjected to the same sequence of reactions as described above, afforded, through the β -keto ester (V), 1:5-dimethylbicyclo-o:3:4-nonane-2:4-dione,

The stereochemistry of 1:5-dimethylbicyclo-o:3:4-nonane-2:4-dione is probably represented either by (IV) with *cis* ring-fusion (Hückel *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1935, 518, 155; Barton, *Experientia*, 1950, 6, 316; Johnson, *ibid.*, 1951, 7, 315) and with the methyl group at C₁ on the β -side, because inspection of the model reveals a considerable non-bonded interaction between the methyl group on the α -side and axial hydrogen atom at C₆, or (IVA).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.'s and b.p.'s. are uncorrected. The U.V. absorption spectrum was determined in 95% ethanol by the Unicam spectrophotometer, S.P. 500.

2-Keto-3-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetic Acid (I: R=H).—(a). A mixture of methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxycyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetate (14.4 g.) and 20% HCl (80 c.c.) was refluxed for 9 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitated oil was extracted five times with ether. The combined ethereal solution was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The cooled alkaline solution was acidified with cold 20% HCl and the precipitated oil was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed once with a small quantity of water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the crude acid (9.3 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether (40–60°) to furnish a crystalline material (5.1 g.), m.p. 89–92°. On concentration of the mother-liquor, another crop of crystals (2 g.), m.p. 90–91°, was obtained. The acid was crystallised three times from the same mixture of solvents to furnish the pure material, m.p. 95°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 236 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.84). (Found: C, 64.65; H, 7.09. $C_9H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 64.27; H, 7.18%).

(b). A mixture of the above substituted β -keto ester (4.8 g.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and 20% HCl (8 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 2 hrs. The cold reaction mixture, after dilution with water and working up, furnished the acid (2.2 g.), m.p. 89–91°.

Alkaline Treatment of Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-3-carbomethoxycyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetate.—The above substituted β -keto ester (12 g.) was refluxed with 10% aqueous NaOH (65 c.c.) for 3 hrs. A further quantity of alkali (20 c.c.) was added to the reaction mixture and the heating continued for 2 hours more. After cooling, the alkaline solution, containing a sweet smelling oil, was extracted with ether. The cooled aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with dilute HCl and the precipitated oil was worked up, as described before, to furnish a gummy residue (5 g.) which was refluxed with methanol (15 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (1 c.c., d 1.84) for 30 hrs. The ester, after working up with ether and saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, was distilled to yield an oil (4.2 g.); b.p. 120–22°/2.5–3 mm, $\lambda_{\max}$ 220 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.61) with inflections at 226–228 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.57) and at 229–232 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.56). (Found: C, 65.09; H, 7.95. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.91; H, 7.73%).

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methylcyclohex- $\Delta^{1:6}$ -enylacetate (I: R=Me).—The crude unsaturated keto-acid (m.p. 90–91°, 10 g.) was refluxed with methanol (30 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (2.5 c.c., d 1.84) for 30 hrs. The ester was distilled to furnish a slightly coloured liquid (9 g.), b.p. 125–26°/3 mm, $\lambda_{\max}$ 230 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.85). (Found: C, 65.45; H, 7.91. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.91; H, 7.73%). The esterification could also be carried out with diazomethane in better yield.

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-6-(diethyl malonate)-cyclohexylacetate (III: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂Et; R₃=Et).—The condensation of diethyl malonate (16.8 c.c.) with the preceding unsaturated keto-ester (12.5 g.) in absolute ethanol (5 c.c.) was performed in presence of sodium (0.05 g.) in absolute ethanol (25 c.c.) according to the procedure of Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 44 hours and after acidification, the product was worked up with ether-benzene mixture. After removal of the solvents, the residue was distilled, b. p. 190–95°/1.5 mm, yield 14.8 g., which was redistilled for analysis, b.p. 185–90°/1.5 mm. The compound is

insoluble in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide. (Found: C, 60.02; H, 7.66. $C_{17}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 59.62; H, 7.65%).

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-6-(ethyl cyanoacetate)-cyclohexylacetate (III: R = Me; $R_1=H$; $R_2=CN$; $R_3=Et$).—To a well-cooled solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.03 g.) and absolute ethanol (10 c.c.), was added dropwise ethyl cyanoacetate (2.7 c.c.) with constant shaking. After 30 minutes, a solution of the unsaturated keto-ester (2.7 g.) in absolute ethanol (4 c.c.) was added dropwise to the enolate with shaking. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 44 hrs. The reddish brown reaction mixture was acidified with cold dilute HCl and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried and distilled to furnish the condensation product (2.1 g), b.p. 180-85°/1 mm. This cyano-ester, in contrast with the malonic ester, is soluble in 10% aqueous NaOH. (Found: C, 61.85; H, 7.62. $C_{18}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 61.01; H, 7.14%).

Dimethyl 3-Methylcyclohexan-2-one-1:6-diacetate (III: R = $R_3=Me$; $R_1=R_2=H$).—The preceding malonic ester (1.7 g.) was heated to boiling with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 15 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 16 hrs. The volatile acids were removed under reduced pressure and the brown viscous residue (1.1 g.) furnished only a small amount of a crystalline material, m.p. 143-44°, when the attempt was made to crystallise the acid from acetone-benzene mixture.

The above cyano-ester (0.7 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) for 30 hours and then HCl was removed under reduced pressure. The residue (0.5 g.) furnished a crystalline material, too small for further purification.

The above crude acid (3.2 g.) in ether (50 c.c.) containing a few drops of methanol was esterified with an ethereal solution of diazomethane. The resulting ester was washed with 5% NaOH solution and distilled, b.p. 150-55°/1.5 mm, yield 2.6 g. (Found: C, 60.92; H, 7.97. $C_{15}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.94; H, 7.84%).

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-6-(diethyl methylmalonate) cyclohexylacetate (III: R = $R_1=Me$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $R_3=Et$).—(a). The methylation of the above malonic ester (14.5 g.) in absolute ethanol (15 c.c.) was carried out by following the method of Mukherjee (*loc.cit.*) with sodium (1.2 g.) in dry ethanol (40 c.c.) and methyl iodide (20 c.c.) by heating on a water-bath for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed by pouring into ice-water containing a few drops of acetic acid. The precipitated oil was worked up by a mixture of ether and benzene. After removal of the dry solvent, the residue was distilled, b.p. 189-95°/1 mm, yield 9.1 g. (Found: C, 60.24; H, 7.67. $C_{18}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 60.67; H, 7.91%).

(b). To a well-cooled solution of sodium dust (0.11 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (5 c.c.) was added a solution of methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(diethyl malonate)-cyclohexylacetate (1.7 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (5 c.c.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 16 hrs. To the resulting dark brown solution was added methyl iodide (2 c.c.) in dry benzene (5 c.c.), and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. The cooled reaction mixture was taken up in ether and the organic solution was washed successively with cold dilute HCl, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After evaporation of the dry solvent, the residue was

evaporatively distilled at $115-20^{\circ}/0.4$ mm, yield 1.1 g. (Found: C, 60.71; H, 7.80. $C_{18}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 60.67; H, 7.91%).

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-6-(ethyl methylcyanoacetate)-cyclohexylacetate (III: $R=R_1=Me$; $R_2=CN$; $R_3=Et$).—To a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.1 g.) and absolute ethanol (10 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath, was added dropwise a solution of methyl 2-keto-3-methyl-6-(ethyl cyanoacetate)-cyclohexylacetate (1 g.) in ethanol (10 c.c.) with shaking. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 30 mins. in the cooling bath when it turned brown. Methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture was immediately heated and refluxed for 4 hrs. Again methyl iodide (1 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for further 2 hrs. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with cold water and the precipitated oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 10% aqueous NaOH solution and water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at $140-45^{\circ}/1.2$ mm, yield 0.9 g. (Found: C, 62.48; H, 7.62. $C_{18}H_{28}ON_2$ requires C, 62.10; H, 7.50%).

Methyl 2-Keto-3-methyl-6-(methyl α -propionate)-cyclohexylacetate (III: $R=R_1=R_2=Me$; $R_3=H$).—The afore-mentioned methylated malonic ester (2.7 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and 20% HCl (20 c.c.) for 18 hours to furnish a gummy acidic material (1.5 g.).

The above methylated cyanoacetic ester (0.8 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 15 c.c.) for 30 hrs. The reaction mixture after cooling was extracted thoroughly with ether to furnish a sticky acidic material (0.45 g.).

The above crude dicarboxylic acid (4.8 g.) in ether (50 c.c.) was esterified with an ethereal solution of diazomethane to afford a colorless ester, b.p. $155-60^{\circ}/2$ mm, yield 3.1 g. (Found: C, 62.78; H, 8.22. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 62.22; H, 8.17%).

5-Methyl-1 or 3-carbomethoxy-hydrindan-2:4-dione.—To a suspension of sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium dust (0.45 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (10 c.c.) and absolute methanol (0.8 c.c.), was added, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, a solution of dimethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-2-one-1:6-diacetate (2.4 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (20 c.c.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for $4\frac{1}{2}$ hours and then cooled and poured into iced HCl (dil.). The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with ether. The combined extract was washed free of acid with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled to furnish the desired product (0.9 g.), b.p. $140-45^{\circ}/1.5$ mm, which gave an intense violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.34; H, 7.27. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 64.31; H, 7.18%).

1:5-Dimethyl-3-carbomethoxy-hydrindan-2:4-dione (V).—The cyclisation of the dimethyl ester (III: $R=R_1=R_2=Me$; $R_3=H$; 2.6 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (20 c.c.) was carried out with sodium dust (0.45 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (20 c.c.) and absolute methanol (0.8 c.c.), in an atmosphere of nitrogen, by heating for 5 hours. The brown-red reaction mixture was worked up, as described before, to afford the β -keto ester (0.8 g.), evaporatively distilling at $85-90^{\circ}/1$ mm. It developed a deep violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 65.73; H, 8.21. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.52; H, 7.59%).

5-Methylhydrindan-2:4-dione (IV: R=H).—A mixture of the preceding β -keto ester (0.7 g), glacial acetic acid (3 c.c.) and 20% HCl (6 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (40 c.c.) and then extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with a saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, saturated sodium chloride solution and a small quantity of water. After evaporation of the ether, the residue was evaporatively distilled at $75-78^\circ/1.5$ mm, yield 0.35 g. (Found: C, 72.59; H, 8.90. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 72.26; H, 8.48%).

The above diketone (0.14 g.) was converted into the semicarbazone (0.2 g.) by the pyridine method. The crude semicarbazone (0.1 g.), m.p. $217-23^\circ$, was heated in methanolic solution with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and a few drops of HCl (conc.). The crude red D.N.P. (0.12 g.) was chromatographed to give a red D.N.P. (0.08 g), m.p. $159-60^\circ$ (decomp.). Two crystallisations from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) furnished the pure bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. $164-65^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 21.18. $C_{22}H_{22}O_8N_8$ requires N, 21.28%).

1:5-Dimethylhydrindan-2:4-dione (IV: R=Me).—The ester (V, 0.75 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and 20% HCl (10 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 10 hours to furnish the desired diketone, evaporatively distilling at $75-80^\circ/1$ mm, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 73.52; H, 8.72. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.30; H, 8.93%).

The bis-2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by following the procedure described before. On crystallisation from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ethyl acetate (1:1) it gave two fractions: (i) a very small amount of yellow crystals, m.p. $218-20^\circ$ (decomp.) which could not be purified due to lack of material and (ii) more soluble orange crystals, m.p. $180-85^\circ$ (decomp.). Three crystallisations of the orange material furnished the pure isomer, m.p. $193-94^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 20.72. $C_{23}H_{24}O_8N_8$ requires N, 20.72%).

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